

Study 1: Interview Questions

1. Which country are you working in?
2. What are your major responsibilities in your company?
3. How many years have you been working in the IT industry?
4. How many years have you been working with containerized applications?
5. What are the domains for which you are developing containerized applications?
6. Based on your experience, did you notice common themes for container security issues?
7. Can you explain the impact of those risks on container systems?
8. Based on your experience, what are containerized applications' most recurring security risks?
9. Are there any specific tools you use for detection?
10. Are these detection tools effective?
11. What are the main causes of the security threats in container systems?
12. Can you explain more about the causes of the security issues?
13. Have you noticed any pattern (tend, similarity) that manifests to container security issues? If so, what are they?
14. Do you have anything else in mind that could be a cause for an insecure container environment?
15. What are the security practices used to mitigate the security issues in containerized applications?
16. Are there any security issues that stay unresolved?
17. In general, what is the developers' average duration to resolve security issues?
18. Are containers secure enough to support application development?